

Pros and Cons of Information Assurance Assessments and Evaluations

By Edwin Amuga

Introduction

Information assurance focuses on the principles, processes, approaches, and practices to make certain the availability and protection of crucial digital assets of systems of information. It analyzes the assurance of information, management and reaction of event, and standards of safety; and it assesses the merging of between the protection of information, the safety of systems of information, and warfare of information. The field evaluates administrative, practical, legal, and moral concerns connected to protecting crucial assets of digital. The services of information assurance assist business in reducing danger through an organized program that safeguards the privacy, availability, and honesty of vital information and systems (Aland, 2008). Assurance of information delivers the appraisal of security, evaluation, and regimented analysis of penetration; hence, guaranteeing the integrity of customer's information and meeting their supervisory needs of acquiescence. Several advantages have been seen with the implementation of information assurance in most organizations. However, limitations also exist and it is important to address such concerns to avoid the occurrence of such problems in future. Of highest priority in the paper is to prepare a proposal on the advantages and disadvantages of evaluations and assessments of information assurance.

Summary of the Topic

The information assurance has profound understanding of the constitutional and regulatory control of the security of information technology and signifies the optimum skill in

planning of information safety, development of policy, assessment of risk, testing of susceptibility, discovery of intrusion, rescue procedures for disaster, management strategies of configuration, coaching, and response to events. The services of information assurance comprise the consulting of the safety of information, implementation of policy and development of process, the obedience of regulation and assessments of security. Other services include recovery of tragedy, investigation of impact and facilities of remediation, design of protection systems and demands of compliance. One of the benefits of information assurance is that it has the capability of providing understanding and notions of issue solution within a difficult and intricate area (Craig, 2007). Another advantage is that assurance of information does not just concern safety by itself, but regarding hope that evidence introduced by the system is precise and is correctly exemplified; its degree of the approval risk level relies on the vital nature of the task of the system.

However, there are various significant concerns when taking into consideration how to enhance information assurance as an approach and as a discipline. There is little knowledge of information assurance as a discipline. For instance, in the case of assessment of risk, when people with inadequate knowledge are included in risk identification, there will be illegal access by hackers who will access data kept in the system. Similarly, when a laptop misses, formal data will be revealed to an unlawful party and harm of reputation to the agency and Minister as encryption of drive has not been activated on all devices of the laptop. Presently, there are fewer metrics of information assurance to appraise the design and measure the development of systems of information assurance, metrics, and rules. Hence, the research will require a thorough method of engineering and particular tools of engineering to comprehend the full issue of information assurance. The research will also present an assessment of risk and framework of management that quantitatively assesses the policies produced from information assurance.

Conclusion

The research paper will cover all the areas that have been discussed above with specific concern to their pros and cons. The paper will go through recent publications on the topic to enhance further the knowledge on the evaluation and appraisal of information assurance and to offer solutions to the limitations presented. The methodology presented will be fruitful in offering evaluations for industries by generating pertinent findings, which will be accomplished by taking into consideration the information value of industries and practices of the business of organizations.

References

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